

THE RÔLE OF ANTISCORBUTICS IN OUR DIETARY

JAMA 1918;71(12;Sept 21):941-943.

By ALFRED F. HESS

This is a cleaned version of Hess' short review on scurvy published in JAMA.

This is part of section 1918;71;(12):937-965:

<https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/article-abstract/219060>

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1918.02600380001001>

Alfred Hess appears to be the most important clinical researcher on scurvy in the early part of the 20th century. There was extensive biochemical research related to scurvy which led to the identification of vitamin C and to the Nobel prize to Albert Szent-Györgyi in 1937; however, Szent-Györgyi was not a committed long-term scurvy researcher and not a clinician.

In 1920, Hess wrote a monograph, which is informative about the clinical aspects of scurvy.

Selections of the monograph are available at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685194>

Hess' papers on scurvy are listed on pp. 17-18 of that summary.

Biographies of Hess are listed on p.16.

The entire 1920 book is available at:

Hess AF. Scurvy: Past and Present (1920)

<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/40505>

<https://digital.library.cornell.edu/catalog/chla2903792>

<https://archive.org/details/cu31924073869996>

<https://archive.org/details/b29823778>

<https://archive.org/details/scurvypastpresen00hess>

<https://archive.org/details/scurvypastpresen00hessiala>

<https://archive.org/details/scurvypastpresen00hessuoft>

<https://archive.org/details/39002086348019.med.yale.edu>

<https://archive.org/details/scurvypastandpr00hessgoog>

<https://archive.org/details/nutritionfoundat0000hess>

<https://openlibrary.org/books/OL6631267M>

In 1923, Hess wrote a book chapter:

Infantile scurvy (Barlow's disease)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15465662>

This text and the scanned original are available at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19000231>

2026-3-13

This annotated version was prepared by:

Harri Hemilä, University of Helsinki, Finland

<https://www.mv.helsinki.fi/home/hemila>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4710-307X>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/?term=hemila+h>

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Hemilä.

THE RÔLE OF ANTISCORBUTICS IN OUR DIETARY ¹

ALFRED F. HESS, M.D. NEW YORK

From one standpoint our foodstuffs may be classified as essential and nonessential, according as to whether or not they are necessary for the maintenance of life and normal growth. Among the former group may be mentioned the proteins, inorganic salts, and the water-soluble and fat-soluble "vitamins" which recently have been the subject of so much discussion. In my opinion the essential group includes also a food factor that is a necessary component of the diet if we would be protected against the development of scurvy.

In view of the present lack of knowledge it would be fruitless to discuss the question of the exact nature of this food factor—whether it should be termed vitamin, whether it is indeed a food substance, or whether it should be regarded merely as an activator or catalyzer of the foodstuffs. What I wish rather to emphasize is that unless the diet of man includes food possessing this antiscorbutic property, scurvy will develop in due course of time. From this point of view, scurvy must be regarded as a deficiency disease. If, however, we would limit this term to diseases brought about by a deficiency of a definite chemical or biologic substance, then we are not at the present time warranted in thus classifying it. Nor is it necessarily true that scurvy is directly brought about by a lack of this accessory food factor. It is quite probable, as brought out elsewhere,² that the lack of this factor leads rather to the development of substances which in themselves occasion the symptoms of the disease.

I have introduced the subject from this angle as its entire relevancy depends on the question of whether there are or are not antiscorbutic foodstuffs. If the protective or curative value of such foods are, as McCollum and Pitz³ have recently contended, merely dependent on their laxative properties, and interchangeable with laxatives, such as liquid petrolatum or phenolphthalein, then scurvy is in no sense what-

1 Read before the joint meeting of the Section on Pharmacology and Therapeutics and the Section on Pathology and Physiology at the Sixty-Ninth Annual Session of the American Medical Association, Chicago, June, 1918.

2 Hess, A. F.: Infantile Scurvy, *Am. Jour. Dis. Child.*, January, 1917, p. 98.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/archpedi.1917.01910010107008>
<https://zenodo.org/records/1500622>

3 McCollum, E. V., and Pitz, W.; *Jour. Biol. Chem.*, 1917, 31, 229.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9258\(18\)86722-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9258(18)86722-9)

soever due to food deficiency, and has not a proper place in this symposium. Observations of many cases of infantile scurvy, however, have convinced us⁴ that constipation plays no essential role in this disease. In reviewing the many cases that we have seen we find that the infants were not constipated to a greater degree than normal babies, and that the disorder bore no parallel relationship to the activity of the bowels. Furthermore, as brought out in a recent paper,² potato, which is a sovereign remedy for scurvy, is not a laxative, and malt soup preparations, which most readily lead to this disorder, are rather laxative than constipating. To this evidence may be added a recent experience that infantile scurvy does not yield to treatment by liquid petrolatum, but that its symptoms are rapidly alleviated by small additions of orange juice to the dietary, so small as to be without apparent effect on the bowels. In this connection we may add an observation that will be referred to again in its relation to the therapy of this disorder, namely, that orange juice, boiled and rendered slightly alkaline, may be given intravenously with signal success; this procedure leads to no laxative action, and it is evident that its effect cannot be explained in this way. The nature of the antiscorbutive potency of orange juice remains as much an enigma today as ever. Recently we made use of "artificial orange juice."⁵ prepared according to the formula of McCollum, who had found it of marked therapeutic value in the scurvy of guinea-pigs. After a trial of three weeks, however, it was found to be ineffective; on substitution of orange juice in the same dosage, the hemorrhage of the gums disappeared within a few days.

p.942, left column

It will be of advantage to digress for a moment to say a few words concerning the relationship of the so-called guinea-pig scurvy to that of human beings. There is great danger of error in translating the results obtained on these animals directly into terms of the human disease. It would seem that much of the confusion of thought and difference of opinion at the present time as to the nature of scurvy is due to the fact

4 Much of this work has been done in conjunction with Dr. Lester J. Unger.

5 This artificial orange juice was prepared from pure inorganic salts, sucrose and crystalline citric acid in proportions similar to those formed in the edible portion of the orange.

that some are thinking of a disease which they have produced in animals, and others of scurvy as they have encountered it in man; furthermore, that some have brought about a disease in animals by means of one diet, whereas others have employed a diet of quite different nature. These divergences can be harmonized only by a study of the pathology of the disease. At present the diagnosis of scurvy in guinea-pigs, in most investigations, is based solely on clinical signs, uncontrolled by microscopic examination of the bones, in spite of the fact that there are osseous changes which are typical of this disease. The pitfall of omitting histologic examination may be judged when we state that recently we have found that guinea-pigs fed on certain diet may manifest typical signs of scurvy and yet microscopic examination of the bones suggests that we are dealing with rickets and not with scurvy. It would seem as if many of the results of Jackson and Moore⁶ are to be interpreted in this way. Gerstenberger,⁷ in a recent article, suggested that some of the scurvy in guinea-pigs might be rickets or pseudoscurvy. At any rate, if we are to avoid great confusion, and a repetition of an error similar to that which delayed for years the differentiation of congenital syphilis from rickets in human pathology, all reports of experimental scurvy should be controlled by careful pathologic examinations.

p.942, right column

Every individual requires a certain amount of anti-scorbutic substance in his dietary, or, to put this statement in a broader way, every nation has need for a per capita quota of foodstuffs containing this necessary food factor, if scurvy is to be avoided. How much

6 Jackson, Leila, and Moore, J. J.: Jour. Infect. Dis. 1916, 19, 478.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/infdis/19.3.478>

7 Gerstenberger, H. J. Am. Jour. Med. Sc., 1918, 155, 253.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18890903>

https://archive.org/details/sim_american-journal-of-the-medical-sciences_1918-02_155_2/page/252/mode/2up

of this type of food is required, in other words, what is the antiscorbutic minimum for the individual or for the nation, is just as little known as is the minimum requirement of other so-called vitamins. The margin of safety over our annual supply is certainly not very great, assuredly not as large as the excess of water-soluble vitamin, which is so abundantly distributed throughout nature, and probably no greater than that of the fat-soluble vitamin, which McCollum has shown to be present to a considerable extent in milk, eggs and the leaves of plants. How scant is the margin of safety in some countries, may be judged from the fact that in Ireland they are dependent for their health in this regard on the potato — when the crop fails, scurvy develops. That we in the United States are not entirely independent of the potato crop for our anti-scorbutic supply was shown in 1916, when, as you remember, we had to depend on an exceptionally poor yield of the previous year. As a result of this potato deficiency, scurvy developed in numerous institutions in the spring; in one there were to my knowledge more than twenty deaths; in another, in which the amounts of vegetables, and more particularly of potatoes, received during the months of January, February and March were far below what were needed and requisitioned, as shown in the accompanying chart, scurvy broke forth in April and attacked more than 200 inmates. It may be added that when 200 cases of frank scurvy are diagnosed in an institution there are probably an equal number of latent cases

which escape observation, for we must remember that it takes about six months of food deprivation for an individual to manifest scurvy.

Scurvy has not only a civil but also a most important military aspect. As is well known, it was at one time the scourge of armies. In de Joinville's⁸ account of the Crusade of Louis XI, we read of its attacking the troops in Palestine; in Lind's classic monograph on this disease, it is recorded that "when the Swedes carried on a war against the Muscovites, almost all of the soldiers of their army were destroyed by the scurvy."⁹ But we do not need to retrace our steps so far to learn of the appearance of scurvy in the army. In the "Medical and Surgical History of the War of the Rebellion" we find the following statements:¹⁰

p.943, left column

"A scorbutic tendency was developed at most of our military posts during the winter season, after the troops had been confined to the use of the ordinary ration with desiccated vegetables. The latter in the quantities failed to repress the disease. At posts which could be readily supplied with potatoes only the taint was manifested, on account of a want of liberality in the issues." And again: "Among the white troops during the five and one-sixth years covered by the statistics, 30,714 cases of scurvy were reported; and 383 deaths were attributed directly to that disease."

In the present war, Harvier¹¹ has reported that he was surprised to find that among some 800 troops of which he had charge, at least 95 per cent, had scurvy in the spring of 1917, and that since then epidemic

8 Additional footnote:

Description of scurvy on the Seventh Crusade by Jean de Joinville (1249).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17341537>

9 Lind, James: Treatise on the Scurvy, London, 1772, p. 178.
<https://archive.org/details/10473277bsb/page/178/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/178/mode/2up>
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt/items?canvas=200>

10 Medical and Surgical History of the War of the Rebellion, Washington, 1888, Part III, pp. 683-684.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10201743>
https://archive.org/details/b21504015_004/page/682/mode/2up

11 Harvier, P.: Paris med., 1917, 7, 394.

centers have been recognized outside of this sector.¹²

While I do not wish to overestimate the importance of this disorder, I do wish to lay stress on the fact that it is a disorder that must be considered both in civil and in military practice, and that unless we distinguish between those foodstuffs which possess and those which do not possess antiscorbutic value, scurvy will cease to be an exceptional disease. In this regard it may be of advantage to summarize some personal experiences with various antiscorbutics, a detailed account of which will be reported elsewhere. We have found that the bran and germ of the wheat seed and brewers' yeast—substances which are so effective in preventing beriberi—are of no value in warding off scurvy. Dehydrated vegetables retain but little of their antiscorbutic power. We have employed dried carrots in two cases of infantile scurvy, and have found it lacking in curative power. It will be remembered from the quotation cited above that such was the experience in the army in the Civil War. The vegetable which we tested had been heated to a temperature of only from 130 to 135 F. and was attractive in appearance and in flavor. However, "the accessory food factor" had evidently been destroyed. It was employed some weeks after drying, having been kept during the interval in paraffined bags. Feeding experiments with animals that were led with dehydrated vegetables obtained from various sources led to the same result. We do not, by any means, wish to deprecate the use of dehydrated vegetables, for we appreciate their food value and the great advantage that they possess on account of their small bulk. However, I would emphasize the fact most strongly that they cannot be considered the food equivalent of fresh vegetables, and that unless they are given in conjunction with fresh vegetables, fresh fruit or other antiscorbutic, the dietary will induce scurvy. It is quite possible that improved methods of preparation, as regards the temperature or the state of moisture in

12 Undoubtedly scurvy has increased recently both in the civil and military population of the warring countries. We read of a marked increase of this disorder in the Poor Law hospital in Glasgow (Lancet, London 1917, 2, 21) [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(01\)48259-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(01)48259-6) as well as in the Poor Law infirmary of Newcastle (Brit. Med. Jour., 1917, 2, 46). <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.2.2950.46>
In both instances this increase is attributed to replacing potato in the dietary by bread. From Russia comes a report of the occurrence of 500 cases in Petrograd (Russk. Vrach. 1916, 15, 1216). During the spring of 1917, according to Ferrari, an outbreak associated with neuritis invalidated Italian troops on active service (Gazz. d. osp., 1917, 38, 778).

connection with the dehydration may make it possible to overcome this limitation.

The same defect that applies to dried vegetables seems to hold in regard to fruits. From personal experience, at least, I can state that prunes, which are used so extensively in the dietary of infants, possess practically no antiscorbutic power. In this connection I may add that the banana, which would be of great value in this respect, on account of its ready preservation throughout the winter, seems to be singularly poor in antiscorbutic power.

It is clear that there is a need, not only of an exact inventory of antiscorbutic foodstuffs, such as has been recently undertaken by the Lister Institute,¹³ but of efforts directed to enlarge their number. Looking toward this end, I suggested a few years ago the use of the orange peel, instead of or in conjunction with the juice of the orange, in the dietary of infants who are not receiving fresh food. Since this time I have made use of an infusion of the peel¹⁴ in a large infant asylum, and found it entirely satisfactory. I bring this forward as a suggestion for making use of a waste food product. At a time, when oranges are so expensive, and the cost of food has become such a serious item, both for the individual and for institutions, it seems as if this suggestion may be welcomed by the housewife and baby welfare stations. Some arrangement seems possible whereby hotels would save these orange peels for this purpose. By this procedure we obtain about twice the quantity of antiscorbutic material from the orange.

In closing I wish to revert to a subject I mentioned in the early part of this paper, namely, that orange juice, boiled and slightly alkalized with normal sodium hydroxid, constitutes an excellent antiscorbutic agent for intravenous use. It can be given in doses of 1 ounce without occasioning the slightest reaction. This measure is of interest from the standpoint of the pathogenesis of this disorder, and on account of its rapidity of action might be of therapeutic value in combating a large number of cases of scurvy in the advanced stage of the disease.

13 Chick, H., and Hume, M.: *Tr. Soc. Trop. Med. and Hyg.*, 1917, 10, 141.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0035-9203\(17\)80006-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0035-9203(17)80006-7)

<https://zenodo.org/records/18890617>

See also:

<https://zenodo.org/records/18543473>

<https://zenodo.org/records/18484405>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18623119>

14 The orange peels are washed, grated, and added to twice their volume of boiling water. This is allowed to stand over night, then strained and is ready for use. Sugar is added when necessary to make it palatable.

There are some who are of the opinion that scurvy is of bacterial origin, that it is indeed an infectious disease. This point of view was maintained by the famous Boerhaave and supported by Villemin in the seventeenth century; it is held by many of the physicians in Russia today, and has been emphasized in a recent study on experimental scurvy.⁶ To my mind, when an invasion of micro-organisms occurs it is to be regarded as secondary in nature and merely grafted on the nutritional disorder. I bring this aspect of the subject forward at this time to show the important relationship between nutrition and infection, and furthermore to illustrate by means of this example how simple foodstuffs are able to prevent and to cure a systemic infection. In the case of scurvy the fresh vegetables or fruits protect the tissues, not so much by increasing the immunity of the body fluids, but, as I shall show elsewhere, by rendering normal and impermeable the mucous membranes. This constitutes a most remarkable instance of the broad scope of dietetic therapy.

16 West Eighty-Sixth Street.

Legend to the Figure, see the figure in the attached copy at Zenodo:

A comparison between the requisitioned quantity (in thousand pound units) of potatoes and other vegetables, and the quantity received per month by an institution in which more than 200 cases of scurvy occurred at the beginning of April, 1916. The total height of column represents the amount needed and requisitioned; the solid black portion the amount received. The number of inmates in the institution remained approximately the same. The chart illustrates our great dependence on the potato during the winter months. This is due not only to its intrinsic antiscorbutic potency, but, probably quite as much, to the fact that fully twice as many pounds of potatoes are consumed during the winter as of all other vegetables combined. Therefore, according to present dietary habits, if this crop fails or is dehydrated (devitalized), scurvy will develop in the spring.